

Project CHANGES – Spoke 4

D15 – Implementation of pilot and research studies

– Type E – v1.0

30 September 2025

Deliverable information

Work package	WP4
Deliverable leader	UNISOB
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Deliverable status	Final
Deliverable version	v1.0
Date	30 September 2025

Deliverable history

Version	Release date	Summary of changes	Institution(s)
v0.1	28 September 2025	First draft	UNISOB, DTC
v0.9	29 September 2025	Final draft	UNISOB, DTC
v1.0	30 September 2025	Final version	UNISOB

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4	DTC Lazio	DTC	Member
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1. Introduction

Within the research lines of Spoke 4, one of our main goals is to experiment with the use of virtual (energy-efficient) technologies within defined and representative real-case scenarios. In particular, we aim to experiment with them using different museum and art collection templates to design specific case studies, deriving and applying best practices that can be further adapted and reused in institutions and contexts with similar characteristics. The six templates of museums and art collections identified are described as follows:

- Type A – high-density and innovative museum;
- Type B – natural history and scientific museum;
- Type C – widespread art gallery;
- Type D – sites museums with tangible and intangible heritage and landscapes, among those that have either low or no virtual and digital implementations with a particular focus in southern Italy;
- Type E – historical palaces, labelled as museums, among the most important in the Italian heritage context, including UNESCO sites;
- Type F – demo-ethnic-anthropological museums, including rural culture museums (with less than 20,000 visitors per year), anthropological museums and museums of art and popular traditions.

In this deliverable, we describe the outcomes of the work conducted with the cultural heritage institutions we have contacted that are compliant with **Type E museums (Historical palaces, labeled as museums, including UNESCO sites)**, with whom we have established collaborative research projects. In particular, we have identified a set of cultural institutions with which we have set up specific research projects to put into practice existing and ad-hoc tools developed to provide a system to be freely reusable in a similar context by other cultural institutions not necessarily involved in the project.

Some of these projects, referred to as *"core" case studies*, have been conducted in collaboration with companies that provide implementation efforts and institutions that offer domain-specific cultural knowledge and citizen engagement. The companies involved were selected through a public call for applications, supported by the project's funds (i.e., cascade calls). These *"core" case studies* have also been accompanied by additional *research case studies* aligned with the project templates and goals, which the partners of Spoke 4 have used to experiment with further adoptions of the aforementioned workflow, methodologies and tools within the project's period.

2. "Core" case studies

2.1. RC/3DT: The Queen's apartments in Luigi Vanvitelli's original design for the Royal Palace of Caserta. The recovery and enhancement of the rooms on the third floor of the Royal Palace of Caserta

Outline clear goals and objectives

The RC3DT project (Reggia di Caserta - 3D Digital Twin) responds to the call for proposal of Spoke 4 - Virtual Technologies for Museums and Art Collections under the extended PNRR partnership CHANGES: Cultural Heritage Innovation for Next-Gen Sustainable Society, addressing theme number 9, "The Queen's Apartments in the original design by Luigi Vanvitelli of the Reggia di Caserta. The restoration and enhancement of the spaces on the third floor of the Reggia di Caserta".

The project aims to document, map, and preserve the architectural and historical integrity of the Reggia di Caserta through advanced survey methods and high-quality digital reconstructions, contributing to historical research and cultural heritage preservation.

Namely, the activities included in the project deal with conducting precise laser scans and surveys of selected areas of the Reggia to ensure accurate documentation; creating detailed 3D and 2D reconstructions to support historical analysis, restoration planning, and educational purposes; developing a centralized digital repository to integrate and manage survey data and reconstructions, ensuring accessibility for research and conservation purposes; experimenting with augmented reality (AR) as a supplementary tool to test narrative approaches, enriching visitor experiences by providing supplementary narratives and insights into the historical significance of the spaces, adding an intangible dimension to their understanding.

The Reggia di Caserta, a UNESCO World Heritage site, exemplifies 18th-century royal palace architecture, combining baroque grandeur with functional spaces. It is representative of Type E museums (Historical palaces, labeled as museums, including UNESCO sites) within the Spoke 4 project. The RC3DT project focuses on areas such as the Queen's apartments and the third floor, which have undergone functional alterations over time, obscuring their original design and historical intent. These spaces are in critical need of comprehensive and updated documentation to bridge existing gaps in their historical narrative.

Technologies implemented in the project include high-precision laser scanning to capture spatial data of the noble floor and third floor, with the aim of documenting and analyzing their architectural and historical features. The project will also produce

detailed 3D models and 2D plans, including floor plans, sections, and elevations in .dwg format, enabling their use in restoration projects and educational initiatives. A centralized repository will be developed to store and manage the generated 3D and 2D data, ensuring compatibility with existing museum systems and facilitating access for researchers and cultural heritage professionals. The augmented reality application represents an experimental tool to test innovative storytelling approaches. By offering additional narratives and historical insights, AR app aims at providing visitors with a richer and more engaging experience, complementing the physical exploration of the site rather than replacing it.

The project faces several challenges, including ensuring the precision and interpretive accuracy of 3D and 2D reconstructions, integrating the digital repository seamlessly with existing museum systems, and positioning AR storytelling as a supplementary feature that enhances the understanding of the Reggia's history. However, it presents significant opportunities, such as advancing the documentation and preservation of the Reggia's architectural heritage, providing foundational resources for future restoration efforts, and fostering deeper public appreciation through experimental AR storytelling.

The outcomes of this project will benefit several stakeholders. The museum will gain precise documentation and digital models, enriching its research, conservation, and public education efforts while establishing a comprehensive digital archive aligned with its preservation goals. Local public bodies will see strengthened cultural and academic interest in the Reggia di Caserta, alongside opportunities for collaboration between cultural and technological sectors. Visitors, on the other hand, will enjoy access to richer historical contexts through digital reconstructions and experimental AR narratives, offering an enhanced appreciation of the site's historical and cultural significance.

Describe knowledge sharing among project participants

The knowledge-sharing process among the project participants—UNISOB (the research partner), the Royal Palace of Caserta (the cultural heritage partner), and Digitarca (the winning company)—has been structured to ensure effective communication, alignment of goals, and mutual learning throughout the project's lifecycle.

A key instrument for alignment has been the regular bi-weekly plenary calls organized by UNISOB, namely 10 of them between July 2024 and January 2025. These calls were fundamental in aligning all participants on the operational objectives and methodological guidelines outlined in Spoke 4, which were introduced and explained by UNISOB to the winning company. The plenary calls also provided a forum for

Digitarca to present the methodologies and technologies employed for digitization, such as laser scanning and 3D modeling, and to discuss the implications and potential of these tools. Additionally, progress on Digitarca's acquisition activities at the Royal Palace was regularly discussed, ensuring transparent communication and shared understanding among all partners. UNISOB also used these calls to prepare and guide both the partners in understanding the broader context of the Spoke 4 research efforts.

In addition to the plenary calls, a specific training event for the winning companies was organized by Spoke 4 on December 20, 2024. This session presented the finalized version of the CHANGES Spoke 4 guidelines related to acquisition, processing, and Web3D publication of project data. During the event, participants had the opportunity to review the guidelines' methodology and structure, ask questions to the Spoke 4 team, and provide feedback through a dedicated module. This collaborative process aimed to refine the guidelines to better align with the companies' workflows and practical needs. Notably, the guidelines had already been introduced during the earlier plenary calls, ensuring participants were familiar with their key elements.

To further facilitate knowledge sharing, Digitarca also provided demos and technical deliverables as required by the project. These include D1.1, which encompasses the surveys and reconstructions of the spaces on the first and third floors of the Royal Palace of Caserta; D2.1, featuring high-quality 3D graphic reconstructions based on the surveys conducted in Activity A1 (first and third floors of the Royal Palace). These deliverables provide practical insights into the methodologies and workflows adopted, supporting the project's broader objectives.

The Royal Palace of Caserta, as a project partner, facilitated UNISOB's visits to the historical site, enabling the collection of crucial information for designing the mobile AR app with a focus on UX and historically validated storytelling content. With the support of the cultural heritage partner, UNISOB conducted two site visits to the Queen's Apartments to better understand the spatial dynamics and tourist flows, directly contributing to the planning of the AR application and ensuring the integration of these findings into the project.

Practical training activities for the staff of the Royal Palace of Caserta are planned for a later stage, following the release of the digital twin platform realized by Digitarca. These sessions will ensure that the cultural heritage partner is equipped with the skills necessary to effectively use the developed tools and technologies, reinforcing the collaborative and phased approach of the project.

Describe how the guidelines and prototypes identified (in WP3) have been used (or not)

The acquisition process for the Royal Palace of Caserta was conducted in alignment with the digitization guidelines introduced in WP3, ensuring a methodological and standardized approach to meet the project's objectives. These guidelines served as a foundation for achieving high-quality digital outcomes while maintaining consistency across the project's deliverables.

The project focuses on creating a digital twin, a highly accurate and manipulable virtual replica of the real object, accessible via a proprietary cloud-based platform called SmartCity3D. This platform is specifically designed to manage three-dimensional data generated by advanced laser scanning surveys.

To carry out the surveys, static laser scanning equipment (Leica RTC360 Laser Scanner) was employed. The surveys achieved an accuracy of 1.9 mm at a distance of 10 meters, with the field acquisitions set to a maximum grid size of 5 mm. This technology enabled detailed detection of the morphology of objects using a laser beam that performed a 360° rotation, capturing the geometry and structure of surfaces by determining their 3D coordinates (x, y, z). In addition to geometric data, the scanner captured reflectance values—measuring the amount of laser beam returning to the source, which varies depending on material properties, surface conditions, and degradation levels—and real colors through simultaneous 360° spherical photographic acquisitions (Fig. 2.1.1, 2.1.2).

Figure 2.1.1. 3D laser scanner surveys of the apartments on the main floor.

Figure 2.1.2. Drone-based scanning documentation of the apartments on the noble floor

The culmination of these surveys produced a comprehensive point cloud, a dense collection of data points that accurately represent the surveyed object's morphology and spatial configuration.

Figure 2.1.3. Point cloud of one of the courtyards as seen from the third floor.

Figure 2.1.4. Point cloud of a space on the noble floor.

The post-processing phase transformed the raw data into detailed, high-density point clouds using specialized software, enabling precise virtual reconstruction of the architectural environments (Fig. 2.1.3, 2.1.4). These point clouds, augmented by spherical photographic data, formed the foundation for creating 3D and 2D models integrated into the SmartCity3D repository.

The digitization campaign carried out at the Royal Palace of Caserta produced a rich and multifaceted dataset, including architectural plans, BIM models, and high-definition 3D models of selected artefacts. Three architectural plans at a 1:100 scale were delivered, covering the Piano Nobile, the mezzanine floor, and the third floor of the palace, for a total size of approximately 5.15 MB. The plan of the Piano Nobile documents the principal reception rooms arranged around the four internal courtyards, highlighting the solemn representative spaces at the heart of the Bourbon residence and including environments not normally accessible to the public, such as the Queen's boudoir and the historic libraries. The mezzanine plan, although not explicitly required by the tender, was acquired to ensure continuity and completeness of the palace's distributional system, documenting transitional spaces that connect the Piano Nobile to the upper levels. The plan of the third floor reflects spaces more recently adapted for use by the Air Force Cadet School, capturing their altered layout while ensuring a rigorous geometric representation essential for future restoration and conservation projects. Together, these plans provide a comprehensive foundation for both scholarly research and heritage management.

In parallel, BIM modeling was developed for the same floors, reaching a Level of Development (LOD) 200 but with additional architectural details introduced to capture the historical character of the building more faithfully. Derived directly from Fondazione CHANGES - Cultural Heritage Active Innovation for Next-Gen Sustainable Society

laser scanning and photogrammetric point cloud data, the resulting HBIM model ensures consistency between the 2D CAD documentation and the 3D information environment. It constitutes an integrated tool for conservation planning, facility management, and digital valorization of the monument.

The digitization effort also extended to a selection of artefacts within the Royal Palace, acquired through photogrammetry and processed with Structure from Motion (SfM) techniques to generate high-definition, metrically accurate 3D models. These include the Queen's boudoire (Fig. 2.1.5), a finely decorated vase from the Sala Primavera, a cage-shaped clock, and a lectern with an open book signed by Queen Maria Carolina and preserved in the Library. These objects were chosen for their symbolic and aesthetic significance and are now available for documentation, study, and innovative modes of public engagement, including their integration into the prototypical AR storytelling application. The initial idea behind the AR storytelling application was to reimagine the Queen's Apartments as they were conceived by Luigi Vanvitelli, allowing visitors to experience the spaces through the eyes of Queen Maria Carolina during her life at court and to anchor the narrative to the objects and stories that shaped her daily environment. This vision was subsequently refined through the Changes Spoke 4 dedicated guidelines for AR storytelling (AR storytelling framework), which is built around eight focal decision points. By applying the framework, the design team was able to transform a suggestive concept into a coherent narrative structure, adopting a story-centred orientation and defining clear strategies for connecting spaces, artefacts, and historical episodes. In this way, the framework did not generate the idea itself but provided the methodological scaffolding necessary to turn it into a well-defined application concept (Fig. 2.1.6).

Figure 2.1.5. Queen Maria Carolina's Boudoire

Figure 2.1.6. Screenshots of the app and applied design options taken from the AR storytelling framework

All deliverables were produced in both DWG and BIM formats, structured in accordance with the architectural logic defined in the tender and the specific requirements of the Royal Palace. CAD drawings were organized through coherent layer structures, while BIM models were articulated through families, ensuring clarity and interoperability. All representations respected the required 1:100 scale while also

incorporating a higher level of detail where appropriate, thereby supporting a more in-depth architectural reading. To guarantee alignment with cartographic and GIS systems, the plans and models were georeferenced using the WGS84 UTM33 coordinate system, consistent with the SmartCity3D platform into which the point clouds and panoramic images were integrated. For technical usability, non-georeferenced versions were also delivered, simplifying their integration into standard CAD and BIM software workflows.

As part of the project's third phase, the RC3DT platform was developed as a specialization of the SmartCity3D platform to serve as a comprehensive tool for managing and interacting with the 3D digital twin. The platform supports point cloud management, high-resolution photographic imagery, and the generation of 3D models using the "structure from motion" technique. It provides users with an intuitive interface to interact with different map levels (tile maps), facilitating the creation of geospatial databases and enhancing the accessibility of digital assets (Fig. 2.17).

Figure 2.17 (a) and (b). Visualizations from the RC3DT platform

Through SmartCity3D, users can manipulate and explore GIS geodatabases in both 2D and 3D formats, including augmented reality (AR) integration. This platform also enables continuous updates to the database, supporting real-time querying and data input while offering controlled access to ensure security. The platform's functionality accommodates both operational and viewing-only interactions, making it a robust solution for managing the digital twin of the Royal Palace of Caserta.

The RC3DT platform has been developed by combining open-source Web3D and GIS technologies with a robust backend architecture. On the client side, the web interface is implemented with Angular (MIT license), an open-source framework that defines the overall structure of the application. Angular supports the creation of reusable user interface components, routing between different views, form management, multilingual interfaces, and integration with REST services. Together with Angular, the platform employs RxJS (MIT license), a reactive programming library that manages dynamic data flows. This makes it possible to update layers, maps, and three-dimensional content in real time, to optimize searches through techniques such as debouncing, and to coordinate multiple asynchronous service calls efficiently.

For three-dimensional rendering, the platform relies on Three.js (MIT license), a widely adopted Web3D engine that enables the loading and visualization of complex models such as buildings and furnishings. Three.js provides control over materials, lights, shadows, animations, orbital navigation, and interactive features such as object selection. In parallel, Potree (MIT license) has been integrated for the visualization of dense point clouds using WebGL. Potree supports level-of-detail management through octree structures, distance and section measurements, profile extraction, attribute-based or altitude-based coloring, and efficient handling of very large datasets.

Two-dimensional mapping and geographic information services are managed through OpenLayers (MIT license), a web mapping engine that provides raster and vector layer management, tiled services (XYZ/WMTS), WMS and WFS protocols, projection handling, and interactive functions such as panning, zooming, drawing, and selection. The 2D map view is synchronized with the 3D visualization, allowing users to move seamlessly between cartographic and spatial perspectives.

On the server side, the backend is built on the Microsoft .NET Framework 4.8, which provides the application logic and exposes a set of REST APIs. This layer manages user authentication and authorization, database and third-party service integration, processing jobs, caching, and logging. Spatial analysis and geometric operations are supported by NetTopologySuite (MIT license), which enables buffer creation, intersections, unions, simplifications, and topological validation. It also supports multiple coordinate systems and projections, ensuring accurate queries and geoprocessing functions.

In summary, RC3DT combines Three.js for 3D mesh and scene rendering with Potree for high-density point cloud visualization, supported by a reactive and data-driven interface developed with Angular and RxJS. OpenLayers ensures reliable cartographic integration in 2D, while the .NET backend provides secure and scalable services, enhanced by server-side GIS calculations through NetTopologySuite. Almost all the core components for the client interface and GIS functionality are open-source and released under the MIT license, while the application backend runs on the proprietary .NET Framework 4.8.

Outline the introduction of the technology to museum staff or other involved stakeholders (e.g., local public bodies, tour guides)

The RC3DT platform, building upon the foundations of SmartCity3D, has been designed to serve a wide spectrum of professionals engaged in cultural heritage preservation, analysis, and management. Its primary users include restorers and conservators, who can rely on the system for detailed analyses, documentation of degradation, and integration of photographic and three-dimensional records. Architects benefit from its capacity to study spatial proportions, develop digital reconstructions, and extract both two-dimensional and three-dimensional representations for design purposes. Engineers and structural specialists employ RC3DT for precise dimensional checks, technical assessments, and structural modeling. The platform also supports archaeologists and art historians, offering tools to explore and compare three-dimensional datasets while linking them with historical sources. Public institutions and cultural heritage authorities can adopt the platform to monitor and valorize heritage sites, enabling more informed strategies for digital management. In addition, technical staff and maintenance personnel use RC3DT to plan and document interventions, verify structural conditions, and support day-to-day operations directly on site.

In July, dedicated training sessions were organized to introduce participants (the Royal Palace of Caserta staff) to the use of the RC3DT platform and its companion mobile application. The training was structured into two sessions, held on July 18 and July 24, 2025, from 11:00 to 13:00, for a total of approximately four hours. The first session focused on the web platform, guiding participants through login procedures, account configuration, and familiarization with the user interface and its core functionalities. These included 3D navigation of point clouds, 360° panoramic photographic navigation, creation and management of thematic layers and GIS data, as well as handling cartographic layers. The session also demonstrated automated information extraction procedures, which allow the generation of architectural outputs such as sections and elevations directly from acquired three-dimensional data. The second session was dedicated to the SmartCity3D AR mobile application.

Participants learned login procedures and user interface orientation, and practiced key functions such as map-based navigation, augmented reality navigation, GIS data management via mobile devices, and the handling of multimedia attachments directly linked to assets. Overall, the training enabled participants to acquire both practical and operational skills in desktop and mobile environments, providing comprehensive preparation for the use of digital tools supporting the inventory, management, and enhancement of cultural heritage. This first round of training was delivered to the professionals who had worked most closely with the development team throughout the project. The same training will be replicated for the technical staff of the Royal Palace of Caserta, a group of around ten participants who were not involved during the development phase. This second round of training will take place by the end of September 2025. At the conclusion of these sessions, participants will be asked to complete questionnaires designed to assess perceived usefulness, usability, overall endorsement, and general user experience. In addition, a SWOT analysis will be conducted with the participants, allowing them to reflect collectively on the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and potential risks associated with the platform. The combined feedback will provide valuable input for the refinement and validation of RC3DT.

Describe the experimentation session

As previously described, the evaluation of the RC3DT platform will be conducted with the target users involved in the training activities, who will provide feedback on perceived usefulness, usability, overall endorsement, and general user experience, also contributing to a SWOT analysis of the system.

For the prototypical storytelling application, experimentation will take place during the CHANGES dissemination event on October 17, 2025. Dedicated stands within the Royal Palace of Caserta will be set up where visitors will be able to try the AR demo of the app. Interested participants will be invited to provide feedback by completing short ex-post questionnaires addressing overall endorsement and general user experience. They will also be encouraged to share a few spontaneous comments highlighting perceived strengths and weaknesses. This dual approach, involving both structured and open-ended feedback, will provide valuable insights into the potential of the application and guide future refinements for a tool conceived specifically to the general public. Beyond this evaluation, the app itself has been designed to foster participation by creating a closer and more personal connection between citizens and the cultural heritage of the Royal Palace: the app allows visitors to engage directly with hidden or inaccessible content, such as a 360° exploration of the Queen's boudoir or stories and anecdotes from the life of Maria Carolina linked to specific artworks and details. A further dimension of engagement comes from the possibility of exploring

the palace through the Queen's own perspective, seeing what she would have seen in her private spaces. This narrative device generates empathy and brings users closer not only to the protagonists of the site's history but also to the place itself, reinforcing the sense of intimacy and connection. In addition, after completing the in situ storytelling experience, the application extends the visit beyond the palace itself by allowing users to place three-dimensional models of selected objects in their own homes, interact with them, and play with them as if they were taking a piece of the Royal Palace with them. This symbolic appropriation strengthens the sense of belonging and attachment to the heritage site. In this way, the AR app does not simply provide additional information but makes cultural content more accessible and emotionally resonant, encouraging citizens to establish a more immediate and personal relationship with the Royal Palace of Caserta.

Conclusions

From a technological perspective, the project introduced several innovative elements. At its core is the creation of a high-fidelity three-dimensional digital twin of the Royal Palace, which is not only navigable but also fully measurable and manipulable within a cloud-based web platform (RC3DT built on SmartCity3D). The system integrates advanced surveying techniques, including static laser scanning, mobile mapping systems (MMS), Structure from Motion photogrammetry, and LiDAR, with high-resolution imagery, producing a unified digital environment of unprecedented detail. A further innovation lies in the seamless management and sharing of both two-dimensional datasets (such as DWG files) and three-dimensional content, directly linked to the digital twin. The platform also incorporates integrated GIS functionality, enabling multi-level analysis in both cartographic and 3D environments. Complementing the web solution, a mobile AR application (available for Android and iOS) provides immersive and interactive access to heritage content, while the adoption of digital storytelling strategies opens new pathways for cultural and touristic valorization.

The development process faced several major challenges. Chief among them was the management of very large three-dimensional datasets, especially point clouds and high-resolution imagery, which demand significant storage capacity and advanced optimization strategies. The project also required highly specialized personnel to carry out post-processing and streamline workflows. Ensuring metrological alignment between laser and photogrammetric surveys proved another complex task, as scientific rigor and geometric coherence had to be guaranteed at all times. In addition, building a scalable and performant system that could deliver these data-intensive resources via both web and mobile environments was an ambitious undertaking that demanded careful technical design.

The work also revealed several technical limitations. The sheer weight of the datasets makes them difficult to handle with standard software solutions and creates dependence on high-performance workstations and servers for processing. Questions of scalability remain critical, as querying very large databases can introduce latency and performance bottlenecks. Furthermore, issues of metadata standardization and interoperability with existing institutional systems emerged, underlining the need for stronger alignment with shared frameworks and cultural heritage standards. Looking ahead, future developments will focus on improving data scalability and interoperability, further optimizing performance for both web and mobile platforms, and extending the integration of AR storytelling features to enrich visitor experiences. Enhancing metadata standardization and ensuring seamless exchange with other heritage management systems will also be key priorities, so that the solutions developed can serve not only the Royal Palace of Caserta but also act as a replicable model for broader cultural heritage contexts.

3. Research case studies

3.1. SPAFE – Sculpture, Painting and Architecture Fruition Experience

Outline clear goals and objectives

SPAFE is a technological-scientific, educational, and cultural project that aims to create three-dimensional digital reconstructions of spaces within historic buildings (studies, galleries, chapels), in which the original lighting conditions are virtually restored – not only daylight but also nighttime lighting – according to literary, archival, and historiographical sources. SPAFE also aims to reinsert into the reconstructed virtual environment the works of art that were part of the original ornamental context. The case study of the SPAFE project is one of Italy's most visited historical and museum sites, part of the UNESCO world heritage list: Villa d'Este in Tivoli.

The main challenges in the case study of Villa d'Este are:

- A. The accurate identification of the spaces, such as the so-called "Quarto camerino" of Cardinal Ippolito, considering the architectural alterations of the Villa over almost five centuries. This has a significant impact on the digital reconstruction, which must recover the original lighting conditions of spaces that have been radically altered.
- B. The identification of paintings, sculptures, and furnishings mentioned in 16th century inventories and literary sources, which are currently dispersed across various European museum collections (for example: Firenze, Gallerie degli Uffizi; Modena, Gallerie Estensi; Madrid, Museo del Prado and Museo Thyssen-Bornemisza).

C. The main technical challenge is related to the very nature of the reconstruction of flame-based sources which, unlike electric ones, exhibit fluctuating luminous intensity over time. This introduces discontinuities in the resulting photometric solid, and the need to establish specific technical solutions, to use different measurement strategies and to define an autonomous production process.

SPAFE project has the potential to radically redefine the museum experience. Through digital reconstructions, it is possible to recreate the topography of Villa d'Este as it was in the time of Cardinal Ippolito. At the same time, it is possible to determine the ancient lighting conditions, allowing users to virtually experience the spaces as they were designed in the 16th century.

Describe knowledge sharing among project participants

Methodologies developed:

A. A methodology for the philological reconstruction of a space belonging to a historic building, based on documents regarding its furnishings and original lighting instruments.

B. A methodology for the reconstruction of the BRDF (Bidirectional Reflectance Distribution Function) of the materials that make up the furnishings and interior surfaces, obtained using photographic methods, and their visualization within a real-time rendering engine.

C. A catalog of light sources including their lighting characteristics, for digital visualization and potential integration into a BIM system for the optimization and management of digital – and, where applicable, physical – spaces.

Describe how the guidelines and prototypes identified (in WP3) have been used (or not)

In the following, the digitisation process of the different rooms and documents is explained.

"Sala della Fontanina": The three-dimensional modeling process of the Room is based on a rigorous methodological workflow, which includes the acquisition of high-resolution photographic data, the use of advanced software for image processing (through Structure from Motion and Dense Cloud Generation techniques), and the validation of the model through comparison with documentary sources and historical-artistic studies. The reconstruction primarily relies on photogrammetry, a three-dimensional surveying technique that, through the acquisition and processing of photographic images, enables the generation of a high-fidelity digital model of the

physical reality. The resulting three-dimensional model will be further enhanced through the integration of additional digital data, derived from meticulous virtual modeling aimed at the philological reconstruction of the original furnishings – now lost or dispersed but documented in historical inventories.

"Prima sala Tiburtina": The 3D reconstruction of the first Tiburtine Room is curated by Haltadefinizione – a tech company specializing in the digitization of cultural heritage, with an established record of collaboration with leading museums and cultural institutions worldwide. The reconstruction is carried out through terrestrial laser scanning, a method that ensures highly accurate and high-quality data acquisition. The 3D model will be accessible online via a web browser and will be navigable through a virtual camera system, allowing users to move through the space and illuminate the walls in accordance with their movement, as if holding a lantern.

"Quarto Camerino": For the reconstruction of the Quarto Camerino, datasets for the paintings, the statue and the room have been processed, to get maps for the reconstruction of the BRDF (Bidirectional Reflectance Distribution Function) for the constituting materials of the assets in the interiors. The generation of optimized 3D models from the acquisition campaigns resulted in a mosaicked maps in gigapixel resolution for the apparent colors, the normal maps and the specular reflection maps to model the specific behavior of painting materials; and in an optimized 3D models of 5 paintings including their frames, 1 statue and the surrounding room.

Texts and Documents: A large number of literary sources and documents related to the history of Villa d'Este is made available through the "Scaffale Tiburtino" section on the Horti Hesperidum website. Considerable effort has been dedicated to the first complete transcription of the 1587 Giornale, which enables the reconstruction of the dispersal of some of the most valuable items from Luigi d'Este's inheritance – many of which belonged to the collections of his uncle Ippolito and were housed in the residences of Rome and Tivoli. For the digitization of textual data, an XML (eXtensible Markup Language) markup language is employed. This metalinguistic system uses tags to define and control the semantic structure of textual document elements.

Outline the introduction of the technology to museum staff or other involved stakeholders (e.g., local public bodies, tour guides)

The technology developed during the course of this research will be made available to Villae Tivoli, the single museum institution that encompasses Villa d'Este, Villa Adriana, the Sanctuary of Hercules Victor, the Mensa Ponderaria, and the Mausoleum of the Plautii. This will offer new opportunities for spatial planning, both in terms of defining visitor pathways and in restoring the original lighting conditions. A digital exhibition, to be displayed in the virtually reconstructed "Quarto Cameriano" is currently in preparation.

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Conclusions

The research has made it possible to recover the sixteenth-century modes of experiencing Villa d'Este, enabling a virtual reconstruction of its historical lighting environment. Through the digital reconstruction of specific rooms, it will be possible to create virtual exhibition spaces designed to host temporary displays. These will serve both to reconstruct spaces lost due to the dispersal of the Este collections or to structural changes to the Villa over the centuries, and to support exhibitions of any kind, providing innovative curatorial possibilities at significantly lower costs than traditional exhibitions.

The next step of the research will be the implementation of physical tools that allow for the recreation of the original lighting conditions not only through virtual reconstructions, but also in physical reality. To move forward in this direction, it will therefore be necessary to open new avenues of dialogue with lighting designers and manufacturers of lighting systems, inaugurating an unprecedented synergy capable of redefining the museum experience.

Acknowledgements

We want to thank the personnel of all the cultural institutions involved and all the companies who have helped us in the implementation of these studies.

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